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Inceldom and Developmental Boundaries: A Scoping Review of Influencing Factors

Public registration Updates

Metadata

This is an update to the original registration

This update was made on Aug 06, 2024

Reason for update:

The data collection tools need to be update to include relevant references.

Landing Page

Intended use

This Generalized Systematic Review Registration Form is intended as a general-purpose registration form. The form is designed to be applicable to reviews across disciplines (i.e., psychology, economics, law, physics, or any other field) and across review types (i.e., scoping review, review of qualitative studies, meta-analysis, or any other type of review). That means that the reviewed records may include research reports as well as archive documents, case law, books, poems, etc. This form, therefore, is a fall-back for more specialized forms and can be used if no specialized form or registration platform is available.

Citation

Van den Akker, O. R., Peters, G. Y., Bakker, C., Carlsson, R., Coles, N. A., Corker, K. S., Feldman, G., , Moreau, D., Nordström, T., Pickering, J. S., Riegelman, A., Topor, M., Veggel, N., Yeung, S., Mellor, D., & Pfeiffer, N. Generalized Systematic Review Registration Form. MetaArXiv.. <https://doi.org/g5fj>.

Review Methods

In this section, you register the general type, background and goals of your review.

Type of review

Scoping Review. This protocol was prepared using the JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis' Protocol Template 2024 (JBI Scoping Review Methodology Group, n.d.) and the PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation (Tricco et al., 2018).

References:

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Review stages

Preparation/Pilot Searches, Pilot Screening (of 10 articles), Pilot Extraction (1 source), Search, Screening, Extraction, S

Current review stage

The search stage has begun for the peer-reviewed sources.

Start date

The preparation stage began January 29, 2024. The search stage began July 08, 2024.

End date

The planned end date is April 15, 2025.

Background

The involuntary celibate, or incel, identity originated online in 1997 among efforts to create inclusive spaces for those wanting to form intimate connections but who had encountered repeated frustrations (Taylor, 2018). However, this self-ascribed identity has come to be associated with misogyny, far-right ideology, and racism (Bates, 2020; Czerwinsky, 2023; Sugiura, 2021). Importantly, this international community (Stijelja & Mishara, 2023) has been receiving more notice from English and Spanish-speaking authorities, including governments (Adams et al., 2021), scholars (Czerwinsky, 2023; García-Mingo & Fernández, 2023; Wood et al., 2022), and mental health practitioners (Broyd et al., 2023) due to the public health threat they pose. For example, incels experience psychological distress that may escalate to suicidal tendencies (Broyd et al., 2023; Sparks et al., 2022). Furthermore, male, misogynistic incels may also engage in gender-based violence ranging from sexual violence (García-Mingo & Fernández, 2023; Regehr, 2022) to misogynistic extremism (Meuller, 2024; Regehr, 2022; Tomkinson et al., 2020; Wood et al., 2022), i.e., terrorist acts and ideologies motivated by sexism that function to maintain male dominance (Gentry, 2022). These negative outcomes make it concerning that, internationally, men and boys are adopting a male, misogynistic incel identity, but this review will focus on English and Spanish-speaking regions (Czerwinsky, 2023; García-Mingo & Fernández, 2023).

Given that male, misogynistic incels pose this myriad of public health concerns, prevention and intervention efforts should be leveraged to minimize or eradicate harm when possible. Indeed, various approaches have been suggested to curb these harms. For instance, scholars who consider incels as more prone than other male supremacist groups to committing violence have suggested adapting existing approaches catered to terrorist groups (Tomkinson et al., 2020; Wood et al., 2022). However, there is a dearth of tested or validated approaches tailored to incels, particularly interventions that address the harms associated with this identity beyond mass attacks (Broyd et al., 2023).

The lack of tailored interventions may also be due to a still incomplete understanding of the factors that influence the adoption of the incel identity (Broyd et al., 2023; Messer, 2023; Tomkinson et al., 2020; Wood et al., 2022). In particular, many scholars have focused on searching for psychological and/or social factors (Messer, 2023; Regehr, 2022; Sparks et al., 2022; van Brunt et al., 2021), neglecting biological factors. Per the biopsychosocial model (BPSM), biological, psychological, and social factors may interact to influence how someone perceives themselves (Borrell-Carrió et al., 2004; Engel, 1977). To date, most scholars have not used the BPSM or a biopsychosocial perspective to guide the investigation of incel's identity development, instead focusing exclusively on the role of masculinity (Blake et al., 2020) or concepts and models related to extremist indoctrination (Regehr, 2022; van Brunt et al., 2021; Wood et al., 2022), but none of these theoretical frameworks have emerged as clearly predominant (Broyd et al., 2023). Thus, further investigation is needed to understand the biological, psychological, and social factors associated with adopting this identity to inform interventions addressing internalizing and externalizing behaviors that pose a public health threat to incels themselves and others, particularly women.

The primary purpose of this scoping review is to identify studies and government reports published in English or Spanish since 1997 (inclusive) that characterize the biological, psychological, and/or social factors that influence the adoption of a male misogynistic incel identity over the life course. The secondary purpose is to identify the theories and methodologies utilized by these scholars. Thus, this study aims to provide an overview of scholarship in this field, illuminating these identified biopsychosocial factors to evaluate this scholarship and suggest future directions.

This review will build upon what scholars have already established about incels. This is an emerging field, and there are disagreements about the definition of incel (Czerwinsky, 2023). However, we know that involuntary celibacy has been a focal point of international online communities since Alana self-identified as involuntary celibate in a supportive online space in 1997 (Taylor, 2018). This self-identification would form the basis for the "incel" community (Taylor, 2018). Again, scholars have defined incels in various ways, but commonly, they define incels as cis-gender, heterosexual male misogynists that form part of online communities in the manosphere, which is "a group of male-oriented websites" (Preston et al., 2021, p. 825), who self-defined themselves by their struggles forming intimate and sexual connections with attractive, heterosexual women (Czerwinsky, 2023; Sharp, 2023; Preston et al., 2021). Other scholars find that adhering to aspects of incel ideology and being sexually and/or romantically frustrated is sufficient to be labeled as an incel without the need for self-identification, especially if the individual has committed or planned acts of mass violence (van Brunt & Taylor, 2020). This review will focus on male, misogynistic incels (of any sexual orientation) as identified by the authors of the studies and government reports.

Importantly, the incel community has negatively impacted others as it has been associated with problematic misogynistic ways of experiencing and performing masculinity (Scaptura & Boyle, 2019). Broadly, sexism and hegemonic masculinity are harmful to women and society, in part because men who experience gender role stress may cope with this negatively by indulging in violent fantasies and even perpetrating violence, particularly against women, to reassert their manhood (Scaptura & Boyle, 2019). Given that sexism, in general, is considered harmful, it is important to examine the impact of a male identity centered on misogynistic beliefs (Sharp, 2023; Preston et al., 2021). Notably, media and self-identified characteristics among incels apprehended in connection with physical violence have been able to account for much of the association between gender role stress and violent imaginings (Scaptura

& Boyle, 2019).

Taking into account these concerning violent cognitive imaginings (Scaptura & Boyle, 2019) and hateful views of others (Preston et al., 2021; O'Donnell & Shor, 2022; Scaptura & Boyle, 2019; Sharp, 2023), it is unsurprising that male, misogynistic incels engage in internalizing (Broyd et al., 2023) and externalizing behaviors that pose a public health threat to themselves and others, particularly women (Broyd et al., 2023; Sharp, 2023; Wood et al., 2022). More specifically, incels may internalize this identity in negative ways, such as by struggling with mental health concerns, including experiencing suicidality (Broyd et al., 2023). Perhaps of greater interest to society, incels have been characterized as domestic terrorists or misogynistic extremists (Sharp, 2023; Wood et al., 2022). Incels are associated with both nonviolent acts of extremism, such as spreading harmful or radicalizing ideology in their online communities, and violent acts, including mass murder (Wood et al., 2022). Even on an interpersonal level, incels can pose a threat to women, particularly if they are more prone to imagining raping women (Scaptura & Boyle, 2019) and engage in behaviors like cybersexual violence, e.g., posting revenge pornography online or physical sexual violence (Regehr, 2022).

In light of these grave public health implications, scholars in this emerging field have called for further investigation of the incel community to define its different sub-sets (Czerwinsky, 2023) and the traits, circumstances, or life events associated with adopting an incel identity (Messer, 2023; Sparks et al., 2022; Tomkinson et al., 2020). Various scholars have contributed to this effort, but more work remains. For instance, Messer conducted a qualitative study to illuminate the psychological and social characteristics underpinning a male, misogynistic incel identity by using interviews with anonymous incels, meaning that her findings were not restricted to incels that have been apprehended for misogynistic extremism (2023). While her findings contributed to this field, she also called for further investigation, especially to include other factors. Notably, Wood et al. were the first scholars to focus on violent male incels to develop a Crime Script Analysis (2022). They found that incels were found to experience many of the same struggles as lone actor terrorists, who carry out their attacks independent of group oversight or shared resources (Moskalenko & McCauley, 2011). However, their work did not lead to a definitive typology despite, or perhaps because of, their narrow focus on male incels associated with mass attacks (both those completed and those that were prevented). Similarly, other researchers have attempted to develop typologies or measures that can characterize incels, particularly those who have planned or completed mass attacks (Scaptura & Boyle, 2019; van Brunt & Taylor, 2020). However, these have not been widely adopted or validated (Broyd et al., 2023).

Perhaps most relevant, scholars have conducted reviews to illuminate the factors and experiences that underpin the incel identity (Broyd et al., 2023; Sparks et al., 2022; Stijelja & Mishara, 2023). Broyd et al. conducted a narrative review to discuss the mental health of incels to help practitioners treat this population more effectively and intervene if the clients showed signs of violent tendencies (2023). Sparks et al. highlighted incels' mental health and focused on incels as individuals attempting to date unsuccessfully (2022). Stijelja and Mishara took a broader approach to identifying these factors because they examined biological, psychological, social, etc. factors (2023). Yet, their definition of incel hinges on literal celibacy and includes adult virgins who may not necessarily be incels. Thus, this study fills an important gap by examining biological, psychological, and social factors per the BPSM (Bolton, 2023; Engel, 1977) identified as influencing the adoption of a male, misogynistic identity within a developmental perspective that centralizes biopsychosocial characteristics outside of criminal acts to allow for intervention before violence escalates (Tomkinson et al., 2020).

Popular, intuitive reasoning proposes that sex, or sexual technology, is the most natural intervention (Hanson, 2023) to inceldom, or endorsement of an incel identity (Cottee, 2020) and/or incel ideologies (Broyd et al., 2023). In short, sex is not the solution (Sharp, 2023). Hintz & Baker assert that incels ascribe to a self-defined identity that may be independent of particular sexual experiences and more closely tied to broader life experiences that affect belief in inceldom or fixed negative mindsets around self-worth as a person and as an intimate partner (2021). Their qualitative findings highlighted that some incels who had sex still identified as incels or as simultaneously both an incel and non-incel. Thus, it follows that male misogynistic incels would not necessarily renounce their identity or their misogynistic beliefs even if they have sex. Pointedly, Sharp argues that (misogynistic) incels' main concern is not actual intimacy with women but control over women and social power (2023). According to Sharp, (misogynistic) incels endorse patriarchal views and advocate for returning to cultural practices that emphasize monogamy and undermine female autonomy to allow them more social power and the ability to engage with conventionally attractive women. Consequently, Sharp proposes that appropriate solutions would address the formation of incel beliefs or act as deterrents to harming women.

Self-evidently, the misogynistic beliefs inherent to the male misogynistic identity are problematic. Scholars have differed in their reasoning for labeling incel beliefs as harmful (Czerwinsky, 2023). Some scholars point to the ties between male, misogynistic incels and misogynistic extremism (O'Donnell & Shor, 2022; Tomkinson et al., 2020; Wood et al., 2022), particularly to argue that government resources should be mobilized to address this threat (Tomkinson et al., 2020). However, when Mueller investigated media portrayals of the Plymouth mass attack, she found that newspapers commonly incorrectly conflated incels and misogynistic extremists (2024). Mueller posited that this could undermine public support for measures that conceptualized gender-based violence outside of the context of mass attacks and for the victims of other forms of gender-based violence. Concerningly, she also argued that media portrayals that depict incels as the worst or only perpetrators of gender-based violence might actually provoke misogynistic incel communities if these depictions are interpreted as evidence that society "others" incels unfairly. Thus, while a male, misogynistic identity may be an important precursor to domestic terrorism (Tomkinson et al., 2020; van Brunt & Taylor, 2020), this study frames this identity as inherently problematic to address the multitude of negative impacts without obscuring the broader spectrum of gender-based violence (Mueller, 2024).

Despite taking a broader focus, this study aims to contribute to the characterization of the factors associated with the male, misogynistic incel identity following the recommendations of researchers concerned with misogynistic extremism (Tomkinson et al., 2020; Wood et al., 2022). This study will help identify these factors and guide future research to provide a basis for timely, evidence-

based programming (Broyd et al., 2023; Messer, 2023; Tomkinson et al., 2020) tailored to specific the biological, psychological, or social factors among different age groups, according to the biopsychosocial model (Engel, 1977). Importantly, the biopsychosocial model can be used as a framework because it helps illuminate the various factors affecting an individual (Engel, 1977) to ensure a broader focus than previous research. However, this model's use does not imply that involuntary celibacy is a medical condition. Ultimately, these efforts would help guide public policy (Tomkinson et al., 2020) and inform mental health treatments (Broyd et al., 2023) to help society continue healing from misogynistic influences, bringing us all closer to true gender equality and improving well-being and public health outcomes.

Prior Reviews

Other researchers have conducted reviews of scholarship conducted on incels. Czerwinsky conducted a systematic review that focused on all studies related to incels and found that future works should specify their population of interest more precisely than describing them as simply incels due to the heterogeneity of this community (2023). Her work critically evaluated the research in this emerging field and characterized the ways in which researchers have viewed or defined incels. Again, this review will focus specifically on male, heterosexual incels rather than the entire incel community.

Broyd et al. conducted a narrative review intended for human service professionals, especially clinicians, to use as a resource in evaluating and treating incels for mental health concerns (2022). While this review does illuminate the psychological characteristics associated with incels' perpetration of violence, this review will take a broader approach to examine biological and social factors as well. Additionally, this review will take a developmental perspective to contextualize these factors within the life course. Thus, this scoping review will take a broader perspective.

Stijelja and Mishara conducted a review of incels that highlighted psychological and social factors associated with incels, but they defined incels as adult virgins (2023). Pointedly, incels are not exclusively adult virgins (Czerwinsky, 2023). Furthermore, the researchers did not review biological factors (Stijelja & Mishara, 2023). The researchers did contextualize their findings within the life course insofar as they referred to the social clock and the timing of sexual experiences, but the researchers did not clearly define all factors according to whether they preceded the adoption of an incel identity. Again, this review follows the BPSM to provide a more comprehensive overview of the factors associated with adopting a male, misogynistic incel identity.

This scoping review focuses on two questions: 1) what biopsychosocial factors affect the development of a male, misogynistic involuntary celibate identity over the life course? and 2) what theories and methodologies have scholars used to identify biopsychosocial factors affecting the development of a male, misogynistic involuntary celibate identity over the life course since 1997? These questions are distinct from those previously used to guide reviews of scholarship on incels. Furthermore, a preliminary search of MEDLINE, the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews and JBI Evidence Synthesis was conducted and no current or underway systematic reviews or scoping reviews on the topic were identified. Thus, this review will fill a gap in this field to help map this literature as serve as a foundation for preventative efforts.

Justification of the Design

This study is a scoping review because this design best fulfills the purpose. Surely, an empirical study could show which biopsychosocial factors are associated with an incel identity, but it could not speak to the theoretical frameworks and methodologies used in the field to investigate incel identity development. Thus, conducting a scoping review allows an exploratory investigation of the current state (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005) of this emerging field (Czerwinsky, 2023) to point out gaps in the literature and summarize what is currently known to help inform prevention efforts, which aligns with the purposes for conducting a scoping review (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005).

Scoping reviews may be subjective and iterative in nature, but this does not mean that these reviews are without value (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005; Mak & Thomas, 2022; Thomas et al., 2020). In fact, this may be a feature deriving from the interpretivist and constructivist paradigms underlying this methodology (Mak & Thomas, 2022). These paradigms have been discussed together (Kivunja & Kuyini, 2017) and been termed subjectivist (Thomas et al., 2020). Succinctly, these paradigms posit that reality is not singular or objective because reality depends on the point of view of the individual, who may find different meanings than others due to different life experiences and circumstances (Kivunja & Kuyini, 2017; Mak & Thomas, 2022).

In this vein, various sources of knowledge may be appropriate beyond only peer-reviewed literature (Mak & Thomas, 2022; Mak & Thomas, 2022). This allows a more comprehensive overview of the current state of knowledge and acknowledges the contributions of various stakeholders than other types of review. Furthermore, this allows for an iterative process dependent upon the critical, continuous reflection of the research team (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005; Mak & Thomas, 2022; Thomas et al., 2020). Thus, scoping reviews allow researchers to have access to more sources of knowledge than other types of review and to engage with these deeply to provide a comprehensive understanding of the field.

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Primary research question(s)

What biopsychosocial factors affect the development of a male, misogynistic involuntary celibate identity over the life course?

Secondary research question(s)

What theories and methodologies have scholars used to identify biopsychosocial factors affecting the development of a male, misogynistic involuntary celibate identity over the life course since 1997?

Expectations / hypotheses

This section will serve as an overview of some of the factors that may impact the development of a male, misogynistic incel identity over time. These factors will be organized according to the BPSM. The factors discussed form the basis for the search criteria in the scoping review. This section ends with the remaining search terms.

Biological Factors

Again, according to the BPSM, various factors related to physical health and physiology (Bolton, 2023; Engel, 1977) fit within the definition of biological factors. Thus, physical health conditions, BMI, and genetic factors would all be appropriate avenues of research. In this vein, it is important to consider that factors related to physical appearance, such as BMI, may be especially important to incels. Incels believe that they are rejected because of their unattractive physical appearance (Bates, 2020; Preston et al., 2021; Sugiura, 2021). For example, incels have been noted as specifically concerned about aspects such as height or facial symmetry (Bates, 2020; Sugiura, 2021; van Brunt & Taylor, 2020). Thus, these aspects and related terms were included in the search strategy when appropriate.

Psychological Factors

Beyond the self-evident loneliness in an incel identity, incels experience other emotional and mental health difficulties (Regehr, 2022; Sparks et al., 2023; Stijelja & Mishara, 2023). Members of this community may be neurodivergent, as evidenced by both self-reported data and clinical diagnoses (Sparks et al., 2023; Stijelja & Mishara, 2023). Broyd et al. found that current research suggests an association between autistic spectrum disorder (ASD) and incel identity, particularly incel-motivated mass violence, which symptoms and co-morbid disorders could explain (2023). Incels may also experience self-esteem and body image issues linked to their beliefs that they are not physically attractive enough to be sexually or romantically successful (Preston et al., 2021; Regehr, 2022; Sparks et al., 2023; Stijelja & Mishara, 2023). Broyd et al. suggested incels may consequently struggle with eating disorders, especially when considering their fixation on "looksmaxxing" (2023). Again, incels have been characterized as having a fixation on sex and feeling frustrated (Bates, 2020; Sugiura, 2021; van Brunt et al., 2021), so this sexual frustration may also be an important psychological experience. Incels have been described as having negative coping patterns, particularly regarding substance use (Messer, 2023), related terms were included. In a broad sense, incels may also experience other internalizing conditions like anxiety, especially in social contexts, and depression (Regehr, 2022; Sparks et al., 2023; Stijelja & Mishara, 2023). In fact, when explaining the perpetration of violence by this community, many include these factors in the causal pathway (Lindner, 2023; Preston et al., 2021; Saptura & Boyle, 2020).

Researchers have also suggested that other mental health conditions or personality factors may be linked with inceldom. For example, van Brunt et al. suggested that incels who commit acts of misogynistic extremism are narcissistic (2021). However, Broyd et al. concluded that more research is needed on the connection between personality disorders, and personality traits broadly, and incels in their narrative review (2023). These researchers stated that psychosis should be studied in relation to inceldom. Thus, this study builds on the narrative review conducted by Broyd et al. by expanding their search terms to include more related psychological factors.

Social Factors

Incels may be impacted by a wide variety of social factors. Per the BPSM, it is important to consider factors related to social power and the environment (Bolton, 2023; Engel, 1977). Thus, factors such as demographic information, socioeconomic status, age, or family background are included. Furthermore, broad terms related to environmental contexts are also included. This scoping review also considers other social factors that have been found to relate to inceldom. Broadly, incels have been impacted by political, technological, and cultural changes that have influenced how women seek partners, enabling them to be more selective and exercise greater sexual agency (Lindner, 2023; O'Donnell & Shor, 2022). These changes have been interpreted by incels as explaining their sexual frustration (Preston et al., 2021) and serve as another example of patriarchal backlash in response to feminist gains (Lindner, 2023; O'Donnell & Shor, 2022). This scoping review does not include terms related specifically to dating technology or to women's movements, but such findings will be considered. These terms were excluded because this review is meant to inform prevention efforts that could target malleable social factors instead of historic or irreversible facts. At an interpersonal level, researchers have alluded that the presence of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs), endorsement of insecure attachment styles, and peer victimization may indicate difficulties with their families and peers (O'Donnell & Shor, 2022;

Regehr, 2022; Sparks et al., 2023). Pointedly, avoidant attachment, in particular, is associated with identifying as an incel, which may reflect a defensive and self-isolating strategy undertaken by men who expect to be rejected that serves to perpetuate incels' romantic loneliness (Sparks et al., 2023). A survey study that compared males who identified as incels recruited from Reddit to university students that did not ascribe that label to themselves found that incels had fewer supports in general and engaged in fewer healthy coping processes (Sparks et al., 2023). Thus, this review includes terms related to ACEs, attachment, and bullying.

References

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Dependent variable(s) / outcome(s) / main variables

Development of a male, misogynistic incel identity

Independent variable(s) / intervention(s) / treatment(s)

Biological, psychological, and social factors influencing male, misogynistic incel identity development

Additional variable(s) / covariate(s)

N/A

Software

Zotero 6 for Windows will be used to store initial search results during data collection. Covidence will be used for storing search results, screening, and recording reasons for exclusion. Google Suite will be used to host team coordination materials and the extraction tools and conduct data analysis and synthesis.

Funding

"Research reported in this publication was supported by the University of Florida Clinical and Translational Science Institute, which is supported in part by the NIH National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences under award number UL1TR001427. The content

is solely the responsibility of the authors and does not necessarily represent the official views of the National Institutes of Health." (Adkins, n.d., Thank you, para.1).

References

Adkins, L. (n.d.). Guides @ UF: Covidence: About Covidence. Retrieved July 11, 2024, from <https://guides.uflib.ufl.edu/c.php?g=1071929&p=7804858>

Conflicts of interest

N/A

Overlapping authorships

N/A

Search Strategy

In this section, you register your search strategy: the procedures you designed to obtain all (potentially) relevant sources to review (e.g., articles, books, preprints, reports, case law, policy papers, archived documents).

Databases

PsychINFO, Web of Science Core Collection, KCI-Korean Journal Databases, MEDLINE, Preprint Citation Index, ProQuest Dissertations & These Citation Index, SciELO Citation Index, Black Studies Center(1900 - current), Criminal Justice Database (1981 - current), Digital National Security Archive, Dissertations & Theses @ University of Florida - FCLA, Ethnic NewsWatch, GenderWatch, History Vault, Periodicals Archive Online, Periodicals Index Online, Policy File Index (1990 - current), ProQuest Dissertations & Theses A&I, ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global, PTSDpubs (1871 - current), Publicly Available Content Database, Biological Science Database, Biological Science Index (1946 - current), Science Database, Social Science Premium Collection (1909 - current), Criminology Collection (1975 - current), Criminal Justice Database (1981 - current), National Criminal Justice Reference Service (NCJRS) Abstracts Database (1975 - current), Education Collection (1966 - current), Education Database (1988 - current), ERIC (1966 - current), International Bibliography of the Social Sciences (IBSS) (1951 - current), Politics Collection (1909 - current), PAIS Index (1914 - current), Policy File Index (1990 - current), Political Science Database (1985 - current), Worldwide Political Science Abstracts (1909 -current), Social Science Database, Sociology Collection (1952 - current), Applied Social Sciences Index & Abstracts (ASSIA) (1987 - current), Sociological Abstracts (1952 - current), Social Services Abstracts (1979 - current), Sociological Abstracts (1952 - current), Sociology Database (1985 - current)

Interfaces

The databases were accessed through the University of Florida library system.

PsychINFO - EBSCO

(Web of Science Core Collection & KCI-Korean Journal Databases & MEDLINE & Preprint Citation Index & ProQuest Dissertations & These Citation Index & SciELO Citation Index) - Web of Science

MEDLINE - PubMed

[Black Studies Center(1900 - current), Criminal Justice Database (1981 - current), Digital National Security Archive, Dissertations & Theses @ University of Florida - FCLA, Ethnic NewsWatch, GenderWatch, History Vault, Periodicals Archive Online, Periodicals Index Online, Periodicals Index Online, Policy File Index (1990 - current), ProQuest Dissertations & Theses A&I, ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global, PTSDpubs (1871 - current), Publicly Available Content Database, Biological Science Database, Biological Science Index (1946 - current), Science Database, Social Science Premium Collection (1909 - current), Criminology Collection (1975 - current), Criminal Justice Database (1981 - current), National Criminal Justice Reference Service (NCJRS) Abstracts Database (1975 - current), Education Collection (1966 - current), Education Database (1988 - current), ERIC (1966 - current), International Bibliography of the Social Sciences (IBSS) (1951 - current), Politics Collection (1909 - current), PAIS Index (1914 - current), Policy File Index (1990 - current), Political Science Database (1985 - current), Worldwide Political Science Abstracts (1909 -current), Social Science Database, Sociology Collection (1952 - current), Applied Social Sciences Index & Abstracts (ASSIA) (1987 - current), Sociological Abstracts (1952 - current), Social Services Abstracts (1979 - current), Sociological Abstracts (1952 - current), Sociology Database (1985 - current)] - ProQuest

Grey literature

There will also be various avenues used to access government reports. GovINFO, Congressional ProQuest, Catalog of U.S. Government Publications (CGP), Congress.gov, the Defense Technical Information Center, HeinOnline, and the Homeland Security Digital Library.

[See the previous sections for other databases searching grey literature.]

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Phenomena of Interest

This review will include empirical and theoretical peer-reviewed studies, theses, dissertations, or U.S. government reports describing incels' biopsychosocial factors. Sources that describe these factors, even if not among the primary purposes of these scholars, will be included. Sources that investigate at least one of these areas will be included.

Concept

This review will center on sources that investigate incels. The specific sub-group of interest is male, misogynistic incels. When the specific subset of incels is not explicitly defined, then it will be assumed that the scholars are investigating this sub-group because it is the sub-group that is most commonly studied and implied by the "incel" label (Czerwinsky, 2023). Within the realm of incel research, this review will focus on sources that discuss biological, psychological, or social factors.

Context

Incels form part of an international community (Czerwinsky, 2023), but this review will focus on sources written in English and Spanish due to practical constraints. This review will include any context in which incels, as previously defined, are discussed regarding demographic information or biopsychosocial factors. This includes sources that discuss incels theoretically if they address biopsychosocial factors, including demographic characteristics. This does not include sources in which incels are discussed in an allegorical sense or as part of an analysis of literature. This excludes linguistic studies that highlight portrayals of incels without making reference to their demographic characteristics, biopsychosocial factors, or cultural factors affecting incel identity, development, or behaviors.

Types of Sources

This review will include peer-reviewed academic and grey literature. As such, it will include peer-reviewed empirical and theoretical works, irrespective of methodology. However, it will not include other literature reviews. Theses and dissertations will be included. Finally, U.S. government reports will also be included.

Additional framework: ProPheT (Problem, Phenomenon, Time)

References

Czerwinsky, A. (2023). Misogynist incels gone mainstream: A critical review of the current directions in incel-focused research. *Crime, Media, Culture, 20*(2), 196–217. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17416590231196125>

Query strings

1. PsychInfo, Web of Science, ProQuest, PubMed, Congress.gov, Defense Technical Information Center:

("Incel*" OR "involuntary celiba*" OR "black pill" OR "Red Pill" OR "manosphere" OR "Elliot Rodger" OR "Alek Minassian" OR "Chris Harper-Mercer" OR "Brian Isaack Clyde" OR "Joseph Miner" OR "Carl Bennington" OR "George Sodini" OR "Marc Lepine" OR "Christopher Cleary" OR "David Kaufman" OR "Malik Sanchez" OR "Scott Beierle" OR "Cole Carini" OR "Jean-Claude Rochefort" OR "Tobias Rathjen" OR "Armando Hernandez, Jr.")

AND ("biological factor" OR "physical health" OR "physical condition" OR "genet*" OR "BMI" OR "height" OR "facial symmetry" OR "develop*" OR "Psychological factor" OR "psychological condition" OR "Mental health disorder" OR "Mental illness" OR "Mental disorder" OR "Narcissi*" OR "Borderline Personality Disorder" OR "Autism" OR "Autism Spectrum Disorder" OR "Autistic Spectrum Disorder" OR "Aspergers" OR "Autism Spectrum Condition" OR "ASD" OR "Psychosis" OR "Schizophrenia" OR "Delusional Disorder" OR "Depress*" OR "Suicid*" OR "Self-harm" OR "Sexual frustration" OR "Bipolar" OR "Anxiety" OR "Substance misuse" OR "Substance abuse" OR "Hopelessness" OR "Body Dysmorph*" OR "body image" OR "body dissatisfaction" OR "Self-hatred" OR "Self-loathing" OR "self concept" OR "self-perception" OR "self esteem" OR "self confidence" OR "self perception" OR "Neurodevelopmental Disorder" OR "Head injury" OR "Social factor" OR "Adverse Childhood Experiences" OR "ACEs" OR "attachment" OR "family background" OR "demographic*" OR "age" OR "gender" OR "socioeconomic" OR "peer victim*" OR "bully*" OR "family environment" OR "Environmental factor")

NOT ("inceleme*" OR "incele*" OR "Black Pill Millipede" OR "incell" OR "inceliyor*")

2. GovInfo:

involuntary celib* OR incel OR misogynistic extremism

3. Congressional ProQuest:

("Incel*" OR "involuntary celiba*" OR "black pill")

4. Catalog of U.S. Government Publications (CGP):

misogynistic extremism

5. HeinOnline:

("Incel*" OR "involuntary celiba*" OR "black pill" OR "Red Pill" OR "manosphere" OR "Elliot Rodger" OR "Alek Minassian" OR "Chris Harper-Mercer" OR "Brian Isaack Clyde" OR "Joseph Miner" OR "Carl Bennington" OR "George Sodini" OR "Marc Lepine" OR "Christopher Cleary" OR "David Kaufman" OR "Malik Sanchez" OR "Scott Beierle" OR "Cole Carini" OR "Jean-Claude Rochefort" OR

"Tobias Rathjen" OR "Armando Hernandez, Jr.") AND ("biological factor" OR "physical health" OR "physical condition" OR "genet*" OR "BMI" OR "height" OR "facial symmetry" OR "develop*" OR "Psychological factor" OR "psychological condition" OR "Mental health disorder" OR "Mental illness" OR "Mental disorder" OR "Narcissist*" OR "Borderline Personality Disorder" OR "Autism" OR "Autism Spectrum Disorder" OR "Autistic Spectrum Disorder" OR "Aspergers" OR "Autism Spectrum Condition" OR "ASD" OR "Psychosis" OR "Schizophrenia" OR "Delusional Disorder" OR "Depress*" OR "Suicid*" OR "Self-harm" OR "Sexual frustration" OR "Bipolar" OR "Anxiety" OR "Substance misuse" OR "Substance abuse" OR "Hopelessness" OR "Body Dysmorph*" OR "body image" OR "body dissatisfaction" OR "Self-hatred" OR "Self-loathing" OR "self concept" OR "self-perception" OR "self-esteem" OR "self confidence" OR "self perception" OR "Neurodevelopmental Disorder" OR "Head injury" OR "Social factor" OR "Adverse Childhood Experiences" OR "ACEs" OR "attachment" OR "family background" OR "demographic*" OR "age" OR "gender" OR "socioeconomic" OR "peer victim*" OR "bully*" OR "family environment" OR "Environmental factor")

6. Homeland Security Digital Library:

"Incel*" OR "involuntary celibate*" OR "misogynistic extremism"

When possible, the search strategy included the use of filters and expanders. Expanders included options such as including related words or subjects. Filters included searching within the abstract for the terms, searching for English or Spanish publications, and searching for sources published since 1997 (inclusive). Again, the language restriction was practical. This year was chosen because it was the year when the label involuntary celibate emerged online as a social identity (Taylor, 2018). Full search strategy protocols are available upon request.

References:

Taylor, J. (2018, August 29). The woman who founded the "incel" movement. BBC. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-us-canada-45284455>

Search validation procedure

N/A

Other search strategies

N/A

Procedures to contact authors

Authors may be contacted to provide a copy of their study, thesis, dissertation, or report via email. If the authors do not respond after one week, then the lead researcher will send one follow-up email. Data about these communications can be made available upon request.

Results of contacting authors

N/A. Data can be made available upon request.

Search expiration and repetition

The searches will not be repeated.

Search strategy justification

Please see the prior sections for other information about the query strings.

Other Search Terms

Necessarily, this review includes other terms to find sources related to incel identity development. Primarily, this means that various terms related to inceldom were included, such as incel, black pill, red pill, and manosphere. Again, incels are part of the manosphere and ascribe to the black or red pill ideology (Preston et al., 2021). This review also expands on the search terms developed by Broyd et al. related to incels connected with mass violence (2023) by including all the incels identified by Wood et al. because Wood et al. focused on individuals who were clearly incels (2022) as there is some debate on which attackers should be labeled as incels, especially when the individual has not self-identified in this manner (Meuller, 2024). These incels were included because their notorious acts and/or prominence within the incel community may have made them subjects of interest for research. The search strategy also includes "develop*" to capture aspects related to development, which may help capture sources that speak to the factors that lead to adopting an incel identity over time. Finally, the search strategy includes various search terms that should be excluded. In various pilots, the search strategy lead to multiple thousands of unrelated results because the root "incel" is part of many Turkish words and because "black pill" can also refer to the "black pill millipede." Thus, related terms were excluded using "not."

The databases, interfaces, and grey literature strategies were selected with input from University of Florida librarian Melody Royster,

M.L.S. and the researcher's Master's thesis committee members Kimberly Wiley, PhD., Jenee Duncan, PhD., and William Marsiglio, PhD. These were selected to find peer-review studies, theses, dissertations, and U.S. government reports that included sources related to biopsychosocial factors influencing the development of a male, misogynistic incel identity. Filters and other constraints (e.g., searching only once and not using citation chaining) were applied in accordance with the eligibility criteria and to accommodate the time and cost limitations of a Master's thesis.

References

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Miscellaneous search strategy details

After the abstract screening, if sources are unavailable through the University of Florida libraries' subscriptions or via public access, then sources will be requested via interlibrary loan. If these sources cannot be acquired via the loan, then the authors will be contacted.

Screening

In this section, you register your screening procedure: the procedure you designed to eliminate all irrelevant sources from the results of the search strategy (and retain the relevant sources).

Screening stages

Covidence software will be used to remove duplicates and will be double-checked using Zotero, which can also detect duplicates. The first round of screening will be based on the titles, abstracts, and keywords. The second round of screening will be based on full texts. Both rounds will be conducted by a six-person research team.

Screened fields / blinding

Blinding will not be employed.

Used exclusion criteria

- Studies without demographics OR don't have at least one of the following: biological, psychological, or social factors will be excluded.
- Linguistic studies that highlight portrayals of incels without making reference to their demographic characteristics, biopsychosocial factors, or cultural factors affecting incel identity, development, or behaviors will be excluded.
- Sources in which incels are discussed in an allegorical sense or as part of an analysis of literature will be excluded.
- Literature reviews will be excluded.
- Sources published before 1996 will be excluded.
- Sources in languages other than English or Spanish will be excluded.
- Sources that are not peer-reviewed journal articles, theses, dissertations, or U.S. government reports will be excluded.
- Sources that do not discuss incels will be excluded.
- Sources that only describe femcels or incels that are not male and misogynistic will be excluded.

Screener instructions

Screeners have been instructed to create Covidence accounts and taught how to use this software. Screeners will be instructed to screen only the articles to which they are assigned in each round. Screeners will be instructed to read the title and abstract or the full text to assess if the source meets the legibility criteria (inclusion and exclusion criteria).

Abstract screening:

Some terms included in the queries were added to the highlights related to the inclusion criteria in Covidence to facilitate screening. Similarly, some terms in the exclusion criteria were added to the highlights related to exclusion in Covidence. Screeners will be instructed to use the highlights to aid screening, but should refer to the full eligibility criteria. Screeners will be instructed to select "yes" for sources that meet the full eligibility criteria, "no" for sources that meet at least one of the exclusion criteria or that don't meet the full inclusion criteria, and "maybe" for sources that the screeners do not feel confident meet the eligibility criteria. The lead researcher (this author) will review sources screened as "maybe," and if it is still unclear, then these will be included in the next

round. Screeners will be instructed to record reasons for exclusion in the respective Google Suite document.

Full-Text Round:

Screeners will be instructed to select "yes" for sources that meet the full eligibility criteria, "no" for sources that meet at least one of the exclusion criteria or that don't meet the full inclusion criteria, and "maybe" for sources that the screeners do not feel confident meet the eligibility criteria. The lead researcher (this author) will review sources screened as "maybe," for inclusion. Screeners will be instructed to record reasons for exclusion in the respective Google Suite document.

- [Incel ScR Data Records KM 052624.xlsx](#)

Screening reliability

A six-person team will complete each screening round, including the lead researcher (this author). The sources will be divided among the team members so that each source is reviewed by two team members. Covidence has been configured to automatically move sources to the next round once two screeners have voted. Inter-rate reliability data will be extracted from Covidence.

Screening reconciliation procedure

The lead researcher (this author) will resolve any disagreements.

Sampling and sample size

All sources identified as meeting the eligibility criteria after the full-text screening round will be included.

Screening procedure justification

The use of multiple rounds of screening, eligibility criteria, and reconciliation procedures, as previously described, follow recommended practices for scoping reviews (Peters et al., 2024).

References

Peters, M. D., Godfrey, C., McInerney, P., Munn, Z., Tricco, A. C., & Khalil, H. (2024). Scoping reviews. In E. Aromataris, C. Lockwood, K. Porritt, B. Pilla, & Z. Jordan (Eds.), *JBIM Manual for Evidence Synthesis*. JBI. <https://doi.org/10.46658/JBIMES-24-09>

Data management and sharing

This information will be stored using Google Suite documents that will be downloaded as XLSX or DOCX files. Data files can be made available upon request.

Miscellaneous screening details

N/A

Extraction

In this section, you register your plans for data extraction: the procedures you designed to extract the data you are interested in from the included sources. Examples of such data are text fragments, effect sizes, study design characteristics, year of publication, characteristics of measurement instruments, final verdicts and associated penalties in a legal system, company turnovers, sample sizes, or prevalences.

Entities to extract Updated

The data extracted will include specific details about the source, including the type, citation information, language of publication, main idea, purpose(s) or objective(s), country of the study, definition of incels, sample characteristics, methodology, theoretical foundations, primary findings, limitations, biological factors, psychological factors, social factors, discussion of public health problems related to inceldom, recommendations for preventing the development of an incel identity, and recommendations for intervening once the identity was adopted. Biopsychosocial factors and factors that do not neatly fit into one of these categories will be collected and organized by age (Arnett, 2007; Santrock, 2010) in which they manifest or begin to influence the adoption of an incel identity. Finally, other information regarding the reviewers' questions or comments and names will be recorded for data management.

References

Arnett, J. J. (2007). Emerging adulthood: What is it, and what is it good for? *Child Development Perspectives*, 1(2), 68–73.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-8606.2007.00016.x>

Santrock, J. W. (2010). *Child Development: An Introduction* (13th edition). McGraw-Hill Humanities/Social Sciences/Languages.

Extraction stages

A pilot round has been conducted with one source. After full-text review, the lead researcher will divide the sources to review among the team members, so that each member extracts data from three sources. Then, the leader researcher will review the responses to ensure data quality and determine whether further team training is necessary. If more training is necessary, then the team will extract data from at least source as an example before moving to the final data extraction stage.

Extractor instructions

The team will be provided with verbal instructions summarizing the content in the Ince ScR Team Materials KM 052524.docx file. The lead researcher (this author) will also respond to any questions about these instructions.

- [Ince ScR AB and Data Collection Tools.xlsx](#)
- [Ince ScR Team Materials KM 052524.docx](#)

Extractor masking

N/A

Extraction reliability

For each extraction round, there will be six extractors. Each source will have data extracted by two extractors working independently. Reliability will not be calculated for the entities requiring narrative entry.

Extraction reconciliation procedure

Discrepancies will be resolved by the lead researcher (this author).

Extraction procedure justification

The entities that will be extracted include items suggested by Peters et al., suggested by the previously mentioned committee members, and determined to be important to answer the research questions by the lead researcher (this author) (2024). The lead researcher, as the team member responsible for intellectual design and with the most relevant expertise regarding incels, will resolve disagreements. This will also be pragmatic considering the time and cost constraints of a Master's thesis. Reliability will not be calculated for the entities requiring narrative entry due to pragmatic concerns.

References

Peters, M. D., Godfrey, C., McInerney, P., Munn, Z., Tricco, A. C., & Khalil, H. (2024). Scoping reviews. In E. Aromataris, C. Lockwood, K. Porritt, B. Pilla, & Z. Jordan (Eds.), *JBIMES-24-09*. JBI. <https://doi.org/10.46658/JBIMES-24-09>

Data management and sharing

This information will be stored using Google Suite documents that will be downloaded as XLSX or DOCX files. Data files can be made available upon request.

Miscellaneous extraction details

N/A

Synthesis and Quality Assessment

In this section, you register the procedure for the review's synthesis: the procedure you designed to use the data that was extracted from each source to answer your research question(s). This often includes transforming the raw extracted data, verifying validity, applying predefined inference criteria, interpreting results, and presenting results. Additionally, you register procedures you designed to assess bias in individual sources and the synthesis itself.

Planned data transformations

Data will be aggregated for each source before analysis. Data that is not recorded in sentences can be recoded into dichotomous variables for analysis. Data that is recorded qualitatively can be analyzed in NVivo, such as via directed content analysis.

Missing data

Missing data will be dealt with according to the instructions in the team materials previously mentioned.

Data validation

N/A

Quality assessment

N/A

Synthesis plan **Updated**

This scoping review will include frequency tables and a narrative discussion. The analysis will use statistical methods like frequencies, which will be presented in tables. Information regarding methodology and theoretical frameworks used will be presented primarily quantitatively in tables or figures. The information regarding biopsychosocial factors will be presented in a figure to show which factors are important and when they begin to influence incel identity development. All of this will be summarized narratively, highlighting gaps in the literature identified after aggregating the data in NVivo. Finally, an in-depth narrative problem and solution discussion will be included to suggest prevention and intervention efforts based on these biopsychosocial factors.

Criteria for conclusions / inference criteria

N/A

Synthesist blinding

N/A

Synthesis reliability

The lead researcher will conduct the synthesis under the supervision of a Master's thesis committee.

Synthesis reconciliation procedure

N/A

Publication bias analyses

N/A

Sensitivity analyses / robustness checks

N/A

Synthesis procedure justification **Updated**

Quantitative data analysis, such as charting or mapping, is common in scoping reviews (Peters et al., 2024). A narrative discussion and summary will also be included as this scoping review will form part of a Master's thesis.

References

Peters, M. D., Godfrey, C., McInerney, P., Munn, Z., Tricco, A. C., & Khalil, H. (2024). Scoping reviews. In E. Aromataris, C. Lockwood, K. Porritt, B. Pilla, & Z. Jordan (Eds.), *JBIM Manual for Evidence Synthesis*. JBI. <https://doi.org/10.46658/JBIMES-24-09>

Synthesis data management and sharing

Data will be analyzed in Google Suite and NVivo, so it can be downloaded as XLSX or NVP files. Data files can be made available upon request.

Miscellaneous synthesis details

N/A

